

ROLE OF MICROFINANCE ON ECONOMIC UPLIFTMENT AND DECISION MAKING OF UNDER-PRIVILEGED WOMEN SEGMENT- A STUDY ON SELECT DISTRICT OF WEST BENGAL.

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ABSTRACT

Financial services for the poor, often referred to as microfinance, cannot solve all the problems caused by poverty, but they can help put resources and power into the hands of the poor and low-income, giving them a way to make their own day-to-day decisions and chart their own path out of poverty. This study focussed on the role of microfinance on economic betterment and decision making on underprivileged women segment. The study is based on primary data as well as secondary data. Primary data was collected, through telephonic interview with the help of structured questionnaire, from women borrowers of microfinance in the North 24 Parganas District of West Bengal. 101 respondents had been chosen by Convenient Sampling, who agreed to respond. Frequency Analysis and Cross Tabulation were used for Descriptive Statistics. Chi- Square test for Independence of Attributes and Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test are used to test the hypothesis. The findings concluded that Age and family type were important demographic factors that influence women's decisions in the study area. They took part in decision making process at household level, diversified their profession and economic activities, increased their income and savings. They had started believing in their self-worthiness, confidence, self-reliance and could shoulder better responsibility to a larger extent.

Keywords: Microfinance, Women's Economic Upliftment, Under-privileged, Self-Reliance

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of Study

Microfinance originally started with microcredit, which is the practice of providing extremely small loans to people without a steady source of income, collateral, or credit history. It also aims to assist and revive entrepreneurs who lack the financial support to start a small business or capital from an idea. The purpose of microfinance is similar to that of microcredit issue. Its goal is to provide financial services to help encourage entrepreneurs in poor countries to realize their ideas and get the financial tools available to do so and eventually become self-sufficient. Some of its other key goals include promoting economic development, reducing unemployment, and stimulating small businesses. Additionally, some microfinance institutions offer business and finance training for their clients to start a small business or function effectively as an entrepreneur

Microfinance Models:

- i. Small business and individual entrepreneur banking has revolved around banking services. relationship-based.
- ii. Group service, where several people form a group together to apply for a loan.

When microcredit was created by Bangladeshi social entrepreneur Muhammad Yunus in 1983, microfinance was created simultaneously. In 1983, Yunus established Grameen Bank in Bangladesh. Grameen Bank's focus was initially on providing small loans to entrepreneurs. The bank's revolutionary model became known as "Unity Group Lending". Yunus pioneered this innovative concept. He concedes that dividing a loan among several beneficiaries can reduce transaction costs. Additionally, a group loan is guaranteed by each of the members that the loans will be repaid on time. Not only can members of the group cover,

if necessary, for the other's payments, they will all be penalized if one of them defaults. The resulting social pressures act as a brake on freedom and crime.

1.2 *Meaning of Microfinance*

Microfinance is the provision of financial services to low-income households, business owners and self-employed workers who traditionally do not have access to banking and other services, helping the poor to rise out of poverty. It includes a wide range of services such as credit, savings, insurance, money transfer, as well as non-financial services such as training, consulting, etc.

1.3 *Need for Micro Finance*

These people are in need of credit facilities for several reasons:

- a. their needs are small and arise suddenly
- b. the institutional providers of finance namely the banks demand collateral security which they cannot provide
- c. most of the time, they are in needs of funds to meet their consumption demands, for example, to meet expenses related to education, illness, funerals, weddings for which it is difficult to obtain institution finance
- d. For purpose of investment in income generating activities.

1.4 *Microfinance and Economic Upliftment of Women*

Amid the lack of formal banking services and credit facilities in more remote parts of the country, microfinance institutions have played a commendable role in empowering women and make it easy for them to access credit, in a ready-made form, helping to make their dreams come true. Numerous studies around the world show that women's empowerment is strongly linked to financial inclusion. An independent woman can make a significant contribution to the health and productivity of her family and community.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Rehman et al. (2020) study focused on the role of microfinance in women's empowerment and in poverty alleviation. The researcher used qualitative approach and case study method to analyze the phenomenon in depth in the context of Akhuwat, an interest-free microfinance institution. It was concluded that microfinance brought changes in the lives of women: household conditions, family happiness and social status. Age, education, marital status and family type are important factors influencing women's empowerment. their income to their family.

Datta and Sahu (2016) conducted a joint study to comprehend the role of MFIs and its associated factors towards women empowerment in Paschim Medinipur district of West Bengal. The study was based on primary data of 220 borrowers collected through structured questionnaires and personal observation. The study found that though MFIs acted as a supportive tool for psychological, economic and social empowerment of women

Lavoori and Paramanik (2014) seeks to examine the impact of microfinance and other socio-economic factors on women's empowerment, from the perspective of their participation in decision-making, income generation and employment. do. Research results based on fieldwork conducted in two villages in Andhra Pradesh show that factors such as income, family size and frequency of self-help group meetings have a positive influence on empowerment. for women globally

Nath (2012) highlighted the performance of female clients in the MF program with particular reference to Gobardhana Block in Barpeta District, Assam. The study was carried out by taking both primary data based on a questionnaire and secondary data. Their research results show that the performance of MFIs is disproportionate and this is due to small loan size, lack of training, management/monitoring of SHGs, etc. The positive side is that women in the sector are more efficient and hard-working, although so far, they have been involved in almost exclusively traditional activities, but are specially trained in innovative business ideas. or small-scale industrialization etc will become a reality and can make participating customers more profitable

Loomba (2013) evaluated the role of microfinance in women's empowerment and performance of SHG groups in Ghaziabad district. From the research, she concludes that the use of microfinance loans and its use for productive purposes has a profound effect on economic status, decision-making power, knowledge and satisfaction. self-esteem of female participants in the association program of banks and self - help groups in Ghaziabad district

Sharma (2007) conducted a study to find the women's participation in group based micro credit programs during 2004-2006 in Nepal. For this a descriptive cross section analytic design was adopted and field survey related to women empowerment was carried out. The findings revealed that women played an important role in house-hold decision making process and had greater access to financial and economic resources, greater social network and better bargaining power.

Khan and Raheman (2007) investigated how microfinance works using group lending to alleviate poverty, empower and improve the living standards of the poor in Bangladesh. The sample was selected based on a random sampling technique and participants in microfinance were interviewed. Microfinance has a positive impact on the living standards of the poor and also helps the poor to improve their status

3. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Microfinance empowered underprivileged women borrowers in several aspects of their life. It enabled them to realise their inner strength, confidence, entrepreneurship and responsibility. Limited study has been conducted in North 24 Parganas district of West Bengal about the role of micro finance on their socio-economic upliftment. Hence, this study was undertaken in this district focusing on this issue.

4. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- (i) Is there improvement in the social and economic conditions?
- (ii) Do the Demographic factors influence the decisions of the women borrowers with regard to Amount of loan, use of loan, use of income and repayment of installments?

5. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- (i) To study the socio-economic profile of the women borrowers
- (ii) To examine the demographic factors that influence the decisions of the women borrowers.

6. HYPOTHESES FRAMED FOR THE STUDY

H₀₁: To assess if there is any significant association between Amount of loan and Age of the respondents.

H₀₂: To assess if there is any significant difference between income before and after availing loan of the respondents.

H₀₃: To assess if there is any significant difference between Savings before and after availing loan of the respondents.

H₀₄: To assess if there is any significant association between decision making power on different aspects and Type of Family of the respondents.

7. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The present study is based on Descriptive Research. Descriptive research refers to the methods that describe the characteristics of the variables under study.

Target Segment of Study

The target segment of study is the Women Borrowers of Microfinance in the region of district- North 24 parganas, West Bengal.

Survey Instrument

The telephonic interview was conducted on the basis of a structured questionnaire.

Sample

101 respondents had been chosen by Convenient Sampling, who happily agreed to respond. Convenient Sampling was a practical method for identifying survey respondents, particularly in situations when lists of potential respondents were difficult to obtain.

Sources of Data: The study is based on primary data and Secondary data

- (i) Primary Data was collected by telephonic interview with the borrowers of MFI
- (ii) Secondary data had been sourced from the relevant books, journals, research papers, government reports and websites.

Data Analysis

The data was analyzed with the help of SPSS Software (version 16). Frequency Analysis and Cross Tabulation were used for Descriptive Statistics. Chi- Square test for Independence of Attributes and Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test were used wherever necessary.

8. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

A. Demographic Factors of the respondents

Figure 1: Distribution of respondent according to Age group

It is seen from Figure 1, majority (34%) of the respondents were belonged to the age group of 26 to 35 years in the study area. It is noted that 29% of the respondents were belonged to the age group of 36 to 45 years in the study area. Likewise, 23% of the respondents belonged to the age group of 18 to 25 years. 14% percent of the respondents belonged to the age group of 45 years and above respectively. From this it can be noticed that most of the respondents are of the middle age group.

Figure 2: Marital Status of Respondents

Figure 2 shows the marital status of the respondents where 68% are married, 16% are unmarried, 9% are widow and 7% are divorced. As most of the respondents are married it clearly shows that women beneficiaries are bounded with lot responsibilities like managing household, upbringing their children and other family members this made them to be quite serious in their SHG work and participation

Figure 3: Types of family among the respondents

It is noted from Figure 3, majority (76%) of them belongs to Nuclear Family and 24% percent to Joint Family system respectively. Since majority respondents are from nuclear family, they find more affordable time, in comparison to that of Joint family, towards activities connected with SHG e.g. group promotion, awareness of new schemes, political participation etc.

Figure 4: Education level of respondents

It is observed from Figure 4, majority respondents (42%) are having Secondary level education, 29% are having primary level of education. It is noticed that 9% of the respondents do possess Higher secondary level of education, 3 % belongs to Graduate category whereas 11 % thereof are illiterate but can sign and only 7% are illiterate. It is quite noticeable that majority of the respondents do possess secondary level and elementary level education. It indicates education makes them well informed and enable the respondents to drive for the required amount of borrowing befitting for their business and profession.

Figure 5: Employment status of respondents before availing loan

Figure 5 indicates the employment status of respondents before availing loan. It is seen that 26.7% respondents were employed in Tailoring and Daily wage, 18.8% employed in road side vendor, 13.9% Maid Servant/Cook respectively. Likewise, 8.9% respondents were House-Wife and only 5% from elsewhere.

Figure 6: Employment status of respondents after availing loan

Figure 6 shows the Employment status of respondents after availing loan. Maximum (32%) respondents are employed in Business/Self profession. It can be seen that 23% respondents are employed in business of Readymade Garment. Likewise, 19 %

employed as Road side vendor, 14% employed in Farming & allied activities and 13 % employed in Various Handicraft making respectively.

So, it is clearly understood that respondents who were mainly Daily wage earners, changed their employment to either Business/self-profession or other type of profession as per their planning. Many respondents took up making of readymade garments as a convenient profession since they could take up the job while doing their domestic work. Further, housewife is engaged in several activities/employments after availing the loan.

Table 1: Amount of loan taken by respondents

Amount of loan taken (in Rs)	Frequency	Percent
Below 10000	6	5.9
10001 to 20000	19	18.8
20001 to 30000	22	21.8
30001 to 40000	24	23.8
40001 to 50000	18	17.8
Above 50000	12	11.9
Total	101	100.0

Source: Computed by researcher on the basis of primary data

Table 1 indicates the amount of loan taken by the respondents. Majority (24%) of the respondents have taken loan of Rs 30001 to 40000. Likewise, 22% of the respondents taken loan of Rs 20001 to 30000, 19% thereof Rs 10001 to 20000 and 18 % of Rs 40001 to 50000 respectively. 12% respondents taken loan above Rs 50000 and only 6% of the respondents taken loan below Rs 10,000. So, it is seen that mostly borrowers had taken loan in two ranges i.e Rs 20001 to 30000 and Rs 30001 to 40000 as they felt the amount as adequate for their proposed new employment.

B. Testing of Hypothesis

H₀₁: To assess if there is any significant association between Amount of loan and Age of the respondents.

Table 2 (a): Amount of loan taken by respondents * Age of the respondent Crosstabulation

		Age of the respondent				Total
		18 to 25 yrs	26 to 35 yrs	36 to 45 yrs	46 yrs and above	
Amount of loan taken by respondents	Below 10000	1	3	0	2	6
	10001 to 20000	6	8	4	1	19
	20001 to 30000	1	15	5	1	22
	30001 to 40000	5	4	12	3	24
	40001 to 50000	6	1	7	4	18
	Above 50000	4	4	1	3	12
Total		23	35	29	14	101

Source: Worked out by using the SPSS (version 16)

Table 2(b): Chi-Square Tests

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	34.561	15	.003

Source: Worked out by using the SPSS (version 16)

Interpretation: It is observed that through chi-square test as shown in table: 2(b), p value is less than 0.05, i.e., $0.003 < 0.05$. Thus, Null hypothesis is rejected at 5% level of significance. Therefore, there is significant association between Amount of loan taken and Age of the respondents.

H₀₂: To assess if there is any significant difference between income before and after availing loan of the respondents.

Table 3 (a) Mean Rank of income before and after availing loan of the respondents-

Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test

Ranks				
		N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
Income after availing loan - Income before availing loan	Negative Ranks	0	.00	.00
	Positive Ranks	101	51.00	5151.00
	Ties	0		
	Total	101		

Source: Worked out by using the SPSS (version 16)

Table 3 (b) Results

Test Statistics	Income after availing loan - Income before availing loan
Z	-8.808
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.000

Source: Worked out by using the SPSS (version 16)

Interpretation:

From Table 3 (b) it is observed that p value 0.000 is less than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$) for income before and after availing loan of the respondents. Thus, Null hypothesis is rejected at 5% level of significance. Hence, it indicates that there is significant difference between income before and after availing loan of the respondents

H₀₃: To assess if there is any significant difference between Savings before and after availing loan of the respondents.

Table 4 (a) Mean Rank of Savings before and after availing loan of the respondents-

Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test

Ranks				
		N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
Savings after availing loan - Savings before availing loan	Negative Ranks	0	.00	.00
	Positive Ranks	101	51.00	5151.00
	Ties	0		
	Total	101		

Source: Worked out by using the SPSS (version 16)

Table 4 (b) Results

Test Statistics	Savings after availing loan - Savings before availing loan
Z	-8.898
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.000

Source: Worked out by using the SPSS (version 16)

Interpretation:

From Table 4(b) it is observed that p value 0.000 is less than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$) for Savings before and after availing loan of the respondents. Thus, Null hypothesis is rejected at 5% level of significance. Hence, it indicates that there is significant difference between Savings before and after availing loan of the respondents

H₀₄: To assess if there is any significant association between decision making power on (Use of loan, Use of Income & Repayment of Instalment) and Type of Family of the respondents

Table 5 (a): Decision making (Use of loan, Use of Income & Repayment of Instalment) * Type of Family of the respondents Crosstabulation

		Type of family of the respondents		Total
		Nuclear family	Joint family	
use of loan	Wife	34	6	40
	Husband	11	3	14
	Wife & Husband	24	4	28
	Jointly with family	8	11	19
Total		77	24	101
Use of income	Wife	37	4	41
	Husband	10	3	13
	Wife & Husband	21	5	26
	Jointly with family	9	12	21
Total		77	24	101
Repayment of instalment	Wife	38	4	42
	Husband	11	5	16
	Wife & Husband	23	6	29
	Jointly with family	5	9	14
Total		77	24	101

Source: Worked out by using the SPSS (version 16)

Table 5 (b): Chi-Square Tests

Chi-Square Tests			
Pearson Chi-Square	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
use of loan	15.344	3	.002
Use of income	17.654	3	.001
Repayment of instalment	18.037	3	.000

Source: Worked out by using the SPSS (version 16)

Interpretation:

It is observed that through chi-square test as shown in Table 5(b):

- p value is less than 0.002, i.e., $0.002 < 0.05$. Thus, Null hypothesis is rejected at 5% level of significance. Therefore, there is significant association between decision making regarding Use of Loan and Type of Family of the respondents.
- p value is less than 0.001, i.e., $0.001 < 0.05$. Thus, Null hypothesis is rejected at 5% level of significance. Therefore, there is significant association between decision making regarding Use of income and Type of Family of the respondents.
- p value is less than 0.000, i.e., $0.000 < 0.05$. Thus, Null hypothesis is rejected at 5% level of significance. Therefore, there is significant association between decision making regarding Repayment of instalment and Type of Family of the respondents.

9. FINDINGS

- Majority (34%) of the respondents were belonged to the age group of 26 to 35 years in the study area. It is noted that 29% of the respondents were belonged to the age group of 36 to 45 years in the study area. It can be noticed that most of the respondents are of the middle age group.
- Most of the respondents are married (68%). It clearly shows that women beneficiaries are bounded with lot responsibilities like managing household, upbringing their children and other family members this made them to be quite serious in their SHG work and participation
- Majority (76%) of them belongs to Nuclear Family. Since majority respondents are from nuclear family, they find more affordable time, in comparison to that of Joint family, towards activities connected with SHG e.g. group promotion, awareness of new schemes, political participation etc.
- Majority respondents (42%) are having Secondary level education. It is quite noticeable that majority of the respondents do possess secondary level and elementary level education. It indicates education makes them well informed and enable the respondents to drive for the required amount of borrowing befitting for their business and profession.
- Maximum (32%) respondents are employed in Business/Self profession. It is clearly understood that respondents who were mainly Daily wage earners, changed their employment to either Business/self-profession or other type of profession as per their planning.
- Majority (24%) of the respondents have taken loan of Rs 30001 to 40000. Likewise, 22% of the respondents taken loan of Rs 20001 to 30000. So, it is seen that mostly borrowers had taken loan in two ranges i.e Rs 20001 to 30000 and Rs 30001 to 40000 as they felt the amount as adequate for their proposed new employment.
- It is quite clear that in all three aspects of decision making at household level, wife is playing an important role in decision making indicating women are considered as more empowered than before. table (20)
- There is significant association between Amount of loan taken and Age of the respondents. It is seen from the analysis of hypothesis that Women borrowers belonging to the age group of 26 to 35 years and 36 to 45 years, are availing higher amount of loan.
- There is significant difference between income before and after availing loan of the respondents.
- There is significant difference between Savings before and after availing loan of the respondents.
- There is significant association between decision making power with respect to Use of loan, Use of Income and Repayment of Instalments and Type of Family of the respondents. It is noted that **Wives are** playing the lead role in decision making activities in Nuclear Households.

10. CONCLUSION

Finally, we may arrive to the conclusion from the of the research that microfinance is playing very important role in economic upliftment of the poor, unprivileged women segment of the study district. It has helped them to take part in decision making process at household level, diversify their profession and economic activities, increase their income and savings. They have started believing in their self-worthiness, confidence, and self -reliance to a larger extent

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